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Wood-based policies as a driver for the climate transition

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Abstract. In the context of global accelerating urbanization, the total floor area of buildings is expected to double by 2060, with a significant impact on the environment. While cities made consistent progress towards increasing energy efficiency, accounting for, and reducing embodied emissions for new and renovated constructions represents one critical priority for mitigating this impact and reaching genuine carbon neutrality. Wood is a renewable and carbon-positive material, which can have a meaningful contribution to changing paradigms on net-zero carbon ambitions of cities, but still faces the challenge of an immature integration into urban development policy framework. Through the Horizon 2020 “Build-in-Wood” project we addressed the challenge of translating novel wood building systems, pilots, wood value chains for the construction of multi-storey wood buildings, and promising practices into policy. As a result, we formulate transferable lessons learned, recommendations, and criteria that can serve as guidance for municipalities and policymakers who aim to channel their efforts toward creating a more sustainable built environment by prioritizing wood, either implicitly or explicitly. We achieved this by working on understanding the real needs of cities and territories, the drivers, and the key entry points and preconditions for new policies supporting multi-storey wood buildings and genuine carbon neutrality. Specifically, the findings are based on the close collaboration with seven affiliated cities (Early Adopter Cities in Europe), outlining and integrating the results of (i) Multi-criterial urban planning, strategic and regulatory context analysis, (ii) Participatory and co-design approaches implemented with their local stakeholder ecosystem from the wood construction value chains and (iii) Research of different best practice policies at national, regional and local level from different parts of the globe, that incentives through informative, financial, research or regulatory instruments building with wood. The entire process is presented in the form of a Build-in-Wood Policy Catalogue [1], offering insights on working with Early Adopter Cities and guidance for improving policy, governance, and the decision-making process for subnational governments. The research was not intended to be exhaustive in documenting all existing policies because of the field’s dynamics, but rather to provide an overview and understanding of different policy instruments’ applicability and potential impact.

Keywords: embodied carbon, carbon-neutral policies, multi-storey wood buildings, changing paradigms

1. Introduction

Figure 1. Overview of implicit wood construction support framework at the European level (URBASOFIA, 2021)

The EU's current political and legislative framework aims to support ambitious policy goals aligned with the Paris Agreement, targeting carbon neutrality by mid-century. Since 2020, the European Commission has introduced several policies and strategies to accelerate the climate transition, many of which impact buildings and the construction sector. Among others, these documents emphasize sustainable building practices, promote the use of wood products and long-lived wood products, support sustainable forest management, 'zero emissions building', and innovative projects in the wood construction sector [1].

As a natural, renewable, and low-carbon material, timber has an essential role to play in transitioning to a sustainable, circular economy, enabling a built environment that harmonizes with the natural world. Timber sequesters carbon in forests, stores it in harvested wood products, promotes sustainable forest management, and supports the circular economy through the reuse, recycling, and recovery of wood products for low-carbon energy at the end of a building's life [2].

Despite the documented benefits of multi-storey wood buildings - including high off-site prefabrication potential, rapid construction, lightweight materials, ease of transport and assembly, healthy indoor environment, quiet and dust-free working conditions, and reduced construction waste - several challenges hinder the widespread adoption of wood in the European cities. These challenges include lack of standardization, legislative constraints, lack of know-how and experience, preconceptions about cost versus benefits, lengthy and difficult permitting procedures for wood structures, public perception, or low awareness [1, 3].

In recent years, there has been a significant increase in the construction of wooden buildings in different parts of the globe, reflecting a growing recognition of the benefits associated with bio-based materials, such as wood [4]. However, many European cities still lack sufficient evidence and adequate policy and strategic guidance to address their specific local challenges effectively, while aligning with the EU agenda and reducing their embodied carbon [5].

'Cities are uniquely placed to demand that carbon performance become an integral part of the assessment during every transaction along the entire value chain and that it is integrated into both procurement and building regulations [4].

2. Build-in-Wood project. Working with Early Adopter Cities process

The Horizon 2020 “Build-in-Wood” project (2019-2023, extended to 08/2024, www.build-in-wood.eu) is taking a whole-life carbon perspective on the potential of using timber and promoting multi-storey wood buildings as long-term carbon storages and compensators of CO₂ emissions from human activities. The project is being implemented by an international consortium led by the Danish Technological Institute and brings together seven Early Adopter City (EAC) affiliates across Europe, under the coordination of URBASOFIA: Metropolitan Region of Amsterdam (NL), Braşov Metropolitan Area (RO), Copenhagen (DK), Haringey Borough of London (UK), Innsbruck (AT), Trento (IT) and Trondheim (NO). The main outputs of “Build-in-Wood” are:

- A fully documented, demonstrated, and cost-effective building system suitable for a range of stakeholder needs and end uses and fit for both new construction and retrofitting. The solution was tested via 7 digital pilots in the EACs, considering environmental and socio-economic benefits, as well as the benefits for cities and regions, in future-thinking scenarios;
- An International Community of Wood Construction, connecting timber professionals and stakeholders, including urban and regional planners across the world, providing resources and decision-making evidence to support wood construction and retrofitting;
- BIM library of Build-in-Wood Components;
- Web-based Design Guide to the construction of multi-storey wood buildings based on project developments and pilot projects;
- Build-in-Wood Demonstrator, a living laboratory where the Build-in-Wood system will be showcased, serving as a platform for industry stakeholders to explore and evaluate innovative building materials, components, and systems in real-life conditions;
- Research, case studies, and recommendations for multi-storey wood building support policies[6].

Through the Build-in-Wood implementation, we understood the real needs and challenges of Early Adopter Cities, through a methodological approach composed of three main components:

(1) Through context-based research, we analyzed provisions and connections between different post-2020 legislative and regulatory layers impacting the construction sector, in order to understand the strategic directions informing local EU city policies for climate neutrality by 2050 and the prerequisites of adopting the prescriptive measures of ‘Fit for 55’. This high-level analysis was supplemented by an (i) review of national, regional, and local-level policies and regulations for the built environment and their impact on multi-storey wood building adoption (explicit support, implicit support, neutral or restrictive) and (ii) multi-criterial analysis of the EACs context to understand the main drivers and preconditions and to produce evidence for new policymaking. The former one was based on 73 quantitative indicators over three evaluative dimensions (socio-demographic, environmental, and economic and market context), synthesized in individual city SWOT analyses and a comparative trend assessment [7].

The second component was the (ii) Co-design process, where key quadruple helix stakeholders in each city were involved in surveys and a first round of workshops (180 total participants) to assess and validate the findings of the initial analysis, analyze perceptions on barriers and opportunities for the sector, including implications and priorities for future planning and development [3]. Specific pathways for lowering embodied carbon through planning and new urban policies were explored in two subsequent rounds of workshops (1 - solutions and scenario-building; 2 - policy options and roadmaps), supported by a global best practice Policy Catalogue [1] including 33 pro-wood policies at national, regional and local levels.

Figure. 2 Build-in-Wood Early Adopter Cities and the Methodology model applied to define specific pathways for lowering embodied carbon in the cities (URBASOFIA, 2023)

As a result of the first rounds of workshops in EACs, five core planning and policy challenges have been identified by the cities, together with their stakeholders:

- Supporting a dedicated building in wood policy (stand-alone or integrated a larger embodied carbon policy) and passing specific timber policies (quota, CO₂, and energy requirements);
- Supporting a retrofit-first approach in planning policy that is low-carbon and circularity-oriented;
- Setting targets for embodied energy in planning policy, prioritizing low carbon materials and 'true pricing' of materials;
- Ensuring carbon offsetting, circular economy principles & performance-oriented heritage building refurbishment;
- Updating outdated regulatory frameworks in the context of high retrofitting and new housing needs, with a focus on material use and design for disassembly [3,6].

Within this methodological approach, the Build-in-Wood Policy Catalogue [1] was developed to address identified challenges. It serves two main purposes: (i) as a working resource and evidence-based support for EACs, offering guidance and a decision-making foundation, and (ii) as an overview and knowledge exchange tool showcasing current best practices in the policy and regulatory environment governing the construction sector to a wider group of municipalities. Additionally, it serves as an inspirational resource by highlighting practical approaches and lessons learned from working with EACs in the Build-in-Wood project.

The purpose of this paper is not to delve into the detailed processes undertaken with each Early Adopter City but rather to highlight key findings that can inform policy design elsewhere. Therefore, the paper aims to address two main questions:

- What policy instruments can municipalities employ to lower embodied carbon and create a more sustainable built environment by prioritizing wood (either implicitly or explicitly)?
- What lessons and guiding criteria can be drawn from cities and regions worldwide that have taken significant steps in this direction?

3. Timber-based policies and enforcement instruments

Figure. 3 Wood-support policies at the national level (URBASOFIA, 2023)

Figure. 4 Wood-support policies at the regional and local level (URBASOFIA, 2023)

Figure. 5 Model for best-practice policy in-depth research (URBASOFIA, 2021)

21 out of the 33 policies reviewed and included in the Build-in-Wood Policy Catalogue [1] are European (particularly Northern European), with the rest North American (7), Oceanian (4), and Asian (2). While the oldest policies date to the 1990s ('Wood Works!', Canada, 1998; 'Building of Tomorrow', Austria, 1999), they have been predominantly of an informative and research & development nature. Front-runners in developing regulatory and legislative policies, i.e. criteria have explicitly been introduced only in the mid-2000s, with pioneers such as Japan (The Act for Promotion of Use of Wood for Public Buildings, Law no. 36/2010) and Sweden ('Mer trä i byggandet / More Wood in Construction', 2004) and front-running cities Vaxjo, Sweden (Construction Strategy, 2005), Zurich, Switzerland (the '2,000-Watt Society' project, 2005) and Trondheim, Norway ('TREbyen', 2004) [6].

More recently, Wood Encouragement Policies (WEPs) and new explicit regulations have been increasingly shaping the direction of planning, new urban development as well as regeneration: France prepared legislation mandating that all new public buildings must be made at least 50% from wood or other sustainable materials from 2022, Denmark introduced CO₂ ceilings for building materials (2023), while cities such as Helsinki in Finland introduced Carbon Footprint Criteria of their own. In the case of the Metropolitan Region of Amsterdam, the "Green Deal Timber Construction" (2021) represents a new historical accord of 32 municipalities mandating at least 20% of the planned MRA housing production annually to be constructed in wood or other bio-based materials, from 2025 (AMS Institute, 2021). These policies will produce significant impacts ranging beyond the form and function of the built environment, changing the local economy and job market and challenging the status quo concerning site planning, master planning, and normative regulations [6].

12 out of 33 policies reviewed indirectly support wood in construction within their narrative, primarily emphasizing one of the following aspects in their broader context:

- low embodied energy/construction materials or environmentally friendly/renewable materials use;
- low carbon procurement requirements/criteria for GHG emissions from construction materials;
- fossil-free buildings and construction activities;
- climate-friendly and energy-efficient construction, operation, and renovation of buildings;
- a green and energy-efficient building sector;
- timber construction supply chain improvement;
- workforce development in the forestry and wood processing sector;
- climate requirements for new buildings (i.e EPD/LCA calculations) [1].

Conversely, the vast majority of the documented policies offer explicit support of wood's wider adoption, being framed under one of the following directions:

- motivation raising more stakeholders to choose to build in wood;
- awareness raising on sustainable materials (incl. wood);
- wood-based solutions support through education and training;
- wood for a wide range of products from sustainable harvesting of local forests;
- increment amount/use of wood in construction;
- targets for new buildings that use wood frames;
- targets for the future building stock to be made in wood/biobased materials;
- targets for new wood-based constructions, new buildings that include climate-impact assessments, preferred smaller carbon footprint in load-bearing structure for building permits;
- showcasing wood products use in sustainable ways;
- use of wood in taller buildings encouraged;
- increment production of forests and quality wood;
- economic growth in the timber and wood products industry;
- encourage and facilitate the use of wood for all projects and mandate it in council's projects;
- financial incentives for new buildings using wood/renewable resources;
- wood encouraged in the council's buildings and infrastructure projects;
- model projects developed in wood (new/renovation/public space);
- high-rise wood-based pilot projects [1].

Despite many policies operating in an integrative manner concerning the typology of instruments applied to achieve their objectives, each policy exhibits a primary implementation vector in their nature, which may fall into one of the following: informative and awareness raising; research and development; regulatory and legislative or financial [1].

Policies driven by legislative and regulatory instruments:

- 'Wood Resource Policy' 2030 and 'Wood Action Plan' (WAP) 2021-2025, Switzerland: clear performance targets and indicators to be achieved by 2030: Increase the demand for wood products used for materials by 30%; Increase the use of Swiss wood in Switzerland's total final consumption of wood as material from around 35% (2012) to 40% (2030), based on 4.0 million m³; Exploit the potential for energy wood use of around 6 million m³ or 16 TWh final energy annually;
- 'Zurich's path to sustainable energy use' (2011) and Roadmap (2016), Switzerland: achieve a sustained primary energy use of 2,000 watts per person and emissions of no more than one tonne of CO₂ equivalent per person per year by 2050;

- ‘Voluntary Sustainability Class for Construction’ (FBK), Denmark: set requirements for new buildings after 2023: LCAs calculations for all new buildings; for buildings exceeding 1000 sqm-must adhere to a threshold of 12 kg CO₂ equivalent per square meter/year; 2027 to 2029, further revisions and limitations will be implemented, aiming for CO₂ emissions to reach 9 kg CO₂-eq/m²/year and eventually 7.5 CO₂-eq/m²/year by 2029;
- ‘Green Deal Timber Construction’, Metropolitan region of Amsterdam, Netherlands: at least 20% of the planned MRA housing production annually from 2025 to be made from wood or other biobased materials;
- ‘Växjö Europe’s First Modern Wooden City’, Sweden: Until 2020, 50 % of all new construction will be wood-based; From 2020, 50% of all new construction will be wood-based and should include a climate impact statement; From 2022, buildings with the smallest carbon footprint of the load-bearing structure are preferred for building permits; From 2025, priority shall be given to new construction with the least climate impact from the whole construction (by using LCA/EPD), or similar;
- ‘Low Embodied Carbon and Energy Procurement Policy’, US: impose minimal standards for energy efficiency, materials, and recycling for federal buildings - All projects require EPDs for 75% of materials used & to demonstrate that their emissions fall in the best-performing 80 % of GWP among functionally equivalent products; Larger projects require a building design which should result in a 20% carbon reduction, compared to a baseline building (WLCAs for project’s structure and enclosure);
- ‘Buy Clean California Act’ (BCCA), US: requires agencies to set Global Warming Potential (GWP) limits and submit Environmental Product Declarations (EPDs) for certain materials used for state-building projects;
- ‘CLEAN Future Act’, Canada: includes several provisions: ‘zero energy ready’ buildings after 2030, codes that seek to achieve a 50% reduction in energy consumption for new buildings by 2029 compared to those built under the current codes, Buy Clean Program etc;
- ‘The Act for Promotion of Use of Wood for Public Buildings’, Japan: mandates national and local governments to prioritize the use of wood materials in public buildings with three stories or less;
- ‘Wood First Policy’, New Zealand: encourage the use of wood as a sustainable building material for all projects within the district, while requiring wood to be used in council projects[1].

Policies driven by informative /awareness-raising instruments:

- ‘Wood Works!’, Canada: provide training, networking, direct technical support, facilitate collaboration with research and education institutions, organize workshops;
- ‘Woodbox Travelling Outreach’, Austria: provide information about the importance of incorporating sustainable construction materials through exhibitions worldwide;
- ‘Policy for the use of wood in construction’, Canada: training and technical support: improving the training given to future construction professionals and technologists; expanding the supply of continuous training to reach a varied client base; diversifying the supply of technical support and tools;
- ‘Bosques Asociados’. Buenos Aires program, Argentina: showcase how wood and wood-related products can be used sustainably; students to explore ideas on how to connect best the needs of metropolitan Buenos Aires with the conservation needs of tropical forests in Argentina;
- ‘Wood Encouragement Policy’, Tasmania, Australia: encourages the use of wood and wood products as a preferred material in building and construction procurement solutions, where feasible;

- ‘Skellefteå City of Wood Strategy’, Sweden: raise the motivation for more people to choose to build in wood; identify and detail 41 projects that were built in wood in the city with different architectural programs;
- ‘Wood Encouragement Policy’, East Fremantle, Australia: encourage and facilitate the use of wood in the construction and fit-out, recognize all of the benefits that make wood a smart choice, promote locally produced wood products where possible;
- ‘Climate Strategy for Oslo towards 2030’, Norway: strengthen cooperation with industry to promote zero-emission buildings and construction projects, call on the government to introduce stronger policy instruments and opportunities to set requirements for zero-emission construction activities;
- Wood City (‘Trästad’) Program, Sweden: research and pilot projects to enhance sector knowledge; monitor wood construction projects, present findings at seminars and workshops, foster collaboration with educational and research institutions, and facilitate the growth of supplier groups in the wood construction sector [1].

Policies driven by research and development instruments:

- ‘National Green Technology Policy’ (NGTP), Malaysia: support the development that meets the current and future needs of forestry and wood processing sector;
- ‘Building of Tomorrow Program’, Austria: develop marketable building components and concepts for residential, office, and commercial buildings (both new and renovation) to further use them in demonstration buildings;
- ‘National Forest Program’, Sweden: sustainable forest management, multi-faceted use of forests for more jobs, innovation, and world-class processed forest materials, expansion of knowledge base for sustainable management and conservation of forests;
- ‘Landscape as Carbon Sinks’ project, Scotland: Understand and communicate the forest and wood-based industries’ contributions to Scotland’s economy; investigate potential interventions to be made to accelerate the land sector’s contribution to net zero GHG emissions;
- ‘Carbon Footprint Criteria’, Helsinki: investigate how the calculation of the carbon footprint can be applied in different procurement groups; what kind of criteria could be developed for the carbon footprinting -for successful examples and applicable tools;
- ‘TREbyen Trondheim’ project, Norway: realize a wide range of different model projects characterized by high quality, proper use of wood with a focus on environmental aspects, and good craftsmanship and professional understanding;
- ‘Bio-Economy Strategy for the Inland Region’, Norway: develop Norwegian Wood Cluster, an expert program for increasing the use of wood, Norwegian Forest Seed Center, demand LCAs in public buildings, a processing center for forest plants, long-term investments in forest management;
- ‘Forestry and Wood Processing Workforce Action Plan’, New Zealand: investment in the development of the workforce to stimulate innovation and growth of new timber-derived products [1].

Policies driven by financial instruments:

- ‘Ontario Mass Timber Program’, Canada: funding for research and development of innovative wood products, for pilot building projects that support further changes in building code and provide transferable knowledge; funding post-secondary education institutions to provide skills development and technical training;
- ‘GCWood’ program, Canada: funds for demo projects and activities that increase the use of wood, encourage research that addresses the gap of technical information needed to facilitate

revisions to the National Building Code – providing a non-repayable contribution of up to 100% of a project's eligible incremental costs;

- ‘Wood Building Programme’, Finland: national government funds for the program, government subsidies for municipally funded wood construction projects; grants and support schemes for research and development projects;
- High-rise wood-based building initiative „ADIVbois“, France: demonstrative wood projects receive financial support from Wood Industries Plan (government initiative) for upstream studies, research, and expertise to assess and secure their development;
- ‘Wood Construction Support Programme’, Freiburg: promotes the construction of new buildings with wood and renewable resources through financial incentives: limited to 1.00 €/kg of natural carbon-storing materials or 1.20 €/kg of renewable construction material that is regionally sourced;
- ‘Home-Grown Homes’ Project, UK: foresees to build 250 new residential homes over 4 years, using national and regional-grown timber to boost local supply chains and the rural economy of Wales [1].

In terms of policy initiator, the documented national-level policies were initiated usually by the government, sectoral ministries, or national councils. Not as common, but they could be also initiated by a research institute, a collaborative arrangement between counties; research institutes and market entities, or industry organizations and government agencies. On the other hand, regional policies were initiated mainly by the county authorities (councils, government) or coalitions of regional authorities (Metropolitan Region of Amsterdam), coalitions of labor and environmental groups/ universities, and knowledge and innovation groups. There are several cases in which the policy was initiated by the Ministry (i.e Policy for the Use of Wood in Construction, Quebec; WEP Tasmania;) [1].

Many regional-level policies have an integrative and extensive approach in terms of the types of instruments applied, tackling besides the informative/awareness-raising component of the research and development one, to provide the necessary scientific evidence to build further (e.g develop design guides for net zero whole life carbon, building performance guidelines) [1].

The local level policies were usually initiated by the City Council or a City Council-led organization, which could play on one side the (i) model role, by encouraging the use of wood for all projects, while requiring/testing wood first in municipal projects (Rotorua District), on the other side it could represent an (ii) facilitator encouraging contractors to include wood options in their designs, engaging and supporting local forestry and the building industry professionals or an (iii) contractor, operating through land allocation programs (Växjö) [1].

4. Takeaways: Guiding criteria and recommendations for municipalities

‘It should be stated that timber does not need policies which would artificially inflate its use. Rather, growing demand for timber in construction will come about through sensible policies aimed at reducing carbon emissions, increasing affordable housing supply, and stimulating the low-carbon and circular economies’[8].

Analyse upfront the feasibility and systemic implications of adopting a pro-wood policy, whether implemented through hard instruments (i.e mandating wood at a wider scale, establishing concrete targets and requirements) or soft instruments (i.e wood encouraged when viable based on costs, quality, application, functionality, resources availability, etc.).

While a policy needs to remain flexible in response to evolving territorial circumstances and emerging market opportunities, it's equally critical to ensure alignment and correlation across other key dimensions within the proposed pro-wood policy: (i) with relevant cross-sectoral policy subsystems and initiatives (i.e decarbonisation, built environment, procurement, circularity, forestry) at different

territorial levels that are being implemented or are planned to be developed, (ii) between policy instruments typologies (soft and hard/ informative, research and development, economic, legislative and regulatory) and (iii) with national standards and requirements for wood products and their origin[1].

- Contextual prerequisites

To secure operational efficiency and the long-term viability of the wider adoption of wood in construction, it's crucial to factor in contextual prerequisites. These may include assessing the availability and proximity of forest resources and wood processing facilities to the urban or regional area where the resources will be further used. Maintaining a close geographical relationship between these elements is paramount. An example in this sense is New Zealand, where approximately 40% of wood is harvested within a 100km radius of Rotorua, the country's forestry focal point, and similarly, Skellefteå locates both the forest resources and sawmill within 50km of the city. Other key contextual preconditions may include: (i) building upon existing tradition and knowledge in using wood materials (as observed in places such as Trondheim, Skellefteå or Tasmania), (ii) receptiveness of local authorities and the public towards using wood as a construction material (e.g France), (iii) overall orientation of the city or region towards fostering research and innovation [1].

- Sustainability and optimization of natural resources

To ensure a lower environmental impact, the sustainability, and optimization of existing natural resources, several aspects should be taken into account: (i) the origin of the wood (i.e wood products that meet the local/national standards and certifications, responsibly sourced wood from sustainably managed forests under a certified scheme such as FSC, PEFC), (ii) setting-up a specific threshold for using wood for economic activities (products, buildings), (iii) include directions to optimize the use of available wood resources, balancing domestic demand with potential export [1].

- Attractivity

To increase the appeal of using wood in construction, the municipality can (i) provide financial support and stimuli such as loans, non-repayable funds, grants, and incentives, or reduce fees for research and development projects related to wood, (ii) elevate the quality of domestic wood products and implement enhancement strategies and plans for timber manufacturing and processing industries and (iii) revise the costs accordingly [1].

On the flip side, while financial backing can drive greater interest in implementing policy stipulations, integrating carbon taxes for emissions could offer a more equitable and sustainable approach. Consequently, funding for policy implementation could stem from CO2 taxation (i.e Zurich's initiatives for sustainable energy use in 2011 and its subsequent Roadmap in 2016)[1].

- Land allocation

Over the span of several years, Växjö municipality [9] actively worked with land policy programs as a tool for the wider adoption of wood-building solutions, acquiring vast expertise in the field through several initiatives (‘More Wood in Construction’ (2005), ‘Växjö – The Modern Wooden City’ (2013), and ‘Växjö: Europe’s First Modern Wooden City’ (2018)). The city adopts among its measures:

- Including research partnership as a prerequisite for an agreement between the municipality and developer;
- Municipality’s role as a contractor actively looking for wood-building solutions during their procurement activities;
- Include in the directive from the municipal council a stipulation that wood-based construction solutions shall always be tested at the start of each project;

- Specifying in the building permit process documentation that the municipality's wood building strategy should be taken into special account, being the basis for the design of all new buildings in the area;
- Advise its affiliated companies to test the potential of wood in each new building project where the possibilities of using wood in their projects must be documented;
- Use land allocation contests with requirements for wood construction, where developers have to present their intended solutions to a steering committee [9,1].

Moreover, cities can take into consideration (i) launching a call for expression for both public and private actors to identify and qualify potential land to accommodate future wooden buildings and (ii) establishing the benefits and requirements for the wood development from the beginning of the collaboration, while keeping the entire process clear and simple for the developers [1];

- Communication and Collaboration

Communication, knowledge exchange, and collaboration play pivotal roles in the design and implementation of a wood-support policy.

- Launch public awareness campaigns and share completed/exemplary best practices. Develop and implement awareness-raising initiatives aimed at professionals as well as the wider public, emphasizing the advantages and potential of timber as a construction material (i.e environmental benefits, carbon sequestration capabilities, and positive societal impacts) to encourage its adoption [4];
- Implement collaborative platforms for coordinated efforts. Moreover, specific collaborative forums dedicated to exchanging best practices can facilitate the knowledge exchange by showcasing insights gained, and obstacles to be wary of, thereby fostering deeper comprehension and widespread adoption of timber [4];
- Involve relevant local stakeholders from the entire wood value chain through iterative engagement activities to identify the existing challenges and opportunities, stakeholder perceptions, formulate local scenarios and strategic directions for the future;
- Require extensive feedback from experts and ensure sufficient administrative capacity (policy design and implementation);
- Take into consideration the adoption of flexible/cross-sectoral collaboration mechanisms (i.e public-private, quadruple helix);
- To develop wood construction projects conduct an early dialogue with interested builders, architects, manufacturers, suppliers, developers, and researchers;
- To facilitate the continuous improvement in the operation/implementation of the policy is essential that relevant stakeholders from the field are encouraged to report continuously impediments or lack of technical data or supply;
- Foster mutual support among the involved parties/municipalities. When implementing a high-level pro-wood policy (metropolitan, regional) it is vital to keep an active collaboration with local authorities/provide guidance on the implementation that could be applied to their different local socio-economic contexts;
- Enhance and maintain international collaboration for experience/ knowledge exchange and support during the implementation of the policy;
- Ensure a skilled workforce in the field (i.e provide education opportunities, capacity-building, training, networking, and technical support) [1].

- Pilot projects

While the pilot projects approach serves as an effective evidence-based tool for fostering innovation and sustainability in the construction sector, several upfront aspects can be considered:

- (i) define precise performance targets, quality criteria, and clear milestones, accompanied by a specific monitoring framework focused on indicators to facilitate future evaluation and knowledge dissemination (including potential changes in building codes);
- (ii) categorize projects based on local needs to allow for flexibility (e.g. renovation, new buildings, urban spaces, private/public buildings);
- (iii) take into consideration from the beginning the future adaptability of using wood in different architectural programs (i.e housing, commercial) not just in public buildings, despite this being the kick-start, due to their different functional/structural necessities;
- (iv) establish an advisory team to provide implementation support, monitor progress, ensure communication and visibility of projects, and assist funded projects in accessing various support schemes from other key stakeholders;
- (v) identify a financing model incorporating diverse funding sources while promoting public-private partnerships. In the case of metropolitan/regional partnerships, assist other municipalities in forging agreements with private actors (e.g. builders, start-ups), and identify and enhance business cases within the wood value chain;
- (vi) building an identity around constructing in wood and sharing completed best practice projects could increase attractivity in time, the city/ region being recognized as an innovator and a place of knowledge, providing the basis to drive forward the technological development in the field [1].

- Sustainable public procurement

Northern cities such as Helsinki and Växjö showed that sustainable public procurement is a viable tool through which municipalities can operate in different ways for making wood-building best practices. Setting climate and environmental criteria in the procurement process is still a feasible kick-start option to ensure the sustainable development of the construction sector and further replication of best practices. However, northern cities' practices showed the importance of (i) enough availability within the city/region of wood construction companies that could apply (wood market analysis upfront); (ii) sufficient consideration given to the climate and environmental standards within the procurement brief to have a real impact (i.e at least 20% based on results from other cities in Finland); (iii) monitor the carbon footprint also during the construction process (where a bonus-sanction model can be applied)[1].

Finland acknowledged many years ago that public procurement of wood-based products can be used for supporting the placement of environmentally friendly solutions on the market and the importance of establishing procurement guidelines for public building projects, electronic contracting tools, and testing measurement and assessment tools to establish the carbon storage and carbon footprint in wood building projects [1,10].

Furthermore, through the Finnish National Public Procurement Policy for Wood-Based Products [10] the country, emphasizes various essential aspects to promote the advancement of sustainable public procurement such as a proficient network of expertise and support, crafting tools to aid contracting entities in sustainable operations, enhancing knowledge about sustainable procurement, making pertinent and effective information accessible to contracting entities, securing proper funding and support, enhancing collaboration and communication of exemplary approaches, and introducing nationally standardized operational frameworks to facilitate the tendering process [1].

Moreover, when setting a procurement material-specific policy, consider initially widely used materials and those with the highest level embodied carbon as eligible materials and revise regularly the maximum acceptable GWP for each category of eligible material, in connection with industry improvements over time [1].

- Enablers and support for normative shift

Several instrumental enablers to speed wood wood-related changes within the construction sector (i.e building codes, standards, and regulations) includes (i) synergic complementary actions embedded within the pro-wood policy, (ii) up-to-date research and development for wood products/designs/solutions correlated with (iii) recommendations and explanatory fact sheets related to timber construction to address the technical gaps, (iv) cost-competitive market-specific drivers, (v) demo projects or “flagship projects first” approach [1].

To showcase the potential of wood construction, influence regulatory frameworks, and promote mid-rise wood buildings as a swift construction alternative, a strategy of initiating “flagship projects” first can be adopted (building tall buildings and high-rise wood demo projects first). This will improve performance, increase the city’s attractiveness, and serve as an architectural reference across the globe (ADIVbois initiative, France) [1].

Given the market tendency to be slow in adapting to constant changes, in parallel with the normative shift, additional support may be crucial: approval process of wood constructions optimized (i.e speed up the process for ancillary requests), provide guidance and assistance to relevant entities and revise timber costs accordingly [1].

- Guidance and assistance

To ensure guidance for relevant stakeholders in the construction field on how to use and incorporate wood in construction: develop detailed toolkits (e.g how to apply the policy requirements, design solutions, technical assistance), provide access to an advisory group or steering committee, form a local task force around wood, provide training, knowledge exchanges and networking opportunities or direct technical support [1];

5. Conclusion

Municipalities aiming to promote wood construction should adopt a balanced and context-sensitive approach that considers environmental impact, economic feasibility, and societal acceptance while aligning with relevant cross-sectoral policy subsystems to address contemporary challenges strategically. These include lowering carbon emissions, enhancing affordable housing and resilience, transitioning towards ecological forestry, and propelling the circular economy forward.

Key recommendations include (i) leveraging local resources, knowledge, and tradition, (iii) ensuring sustainability and optimization of natural resources, (ii) assessing local feasibility for applying both hard and soft policy instruments and employing a combination of policy levers, (iii) offering financial incentives to enhance attractiveness for implementation, (iv) integrating sustainability criteria/wood strategies into land allocation, procurement, and permitting processes, (v) foster communication, knowledge exchange and collaboration, (vi) providing comprehensive guidance and assistance to relevant stakeholders in the field, (vii) supporting up-to-date research/development and implementing pilot projects to foster innovation/sustainability in the construction sector and advance regulatory changes.

References

- [1] Rusen M., Reichert S., Elisei P., 2023, 'Build-in-Wood Policy Catalogue. Making wood cities happen: New urban policies for carbon-neutral cities', Build-in-Wood project, GA no. 862820
Available at: https://community.build-in-wood.eu/topics/27438/media_center/file/de999963-83fa-48df-8674-6490d91be132
<https://urbasofia.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/10/Build-in-Wood-Policy-Catalogue-2.pdf>
- [2] Waugh Thistleton Architects, 2024 'Timber Policy. Understanding low carbon policies for timber construction', p. 4, Timber Development UK
Available at: <https://timberdevelopment.uk/resources/timber-policy/>
- [3] Rusen M., Dimitriu S., 2022, 'Stakeholder co-creation and scenario building workshops'. Technical Deliverable D7.4, Build-in-Wood project, GA no. 862820
- [4] Carbon Neutral Cities Alliance, ARUP, BUILT BY NATURE, Laudes Foundation, 2023, 'City Handbook for Carbon Neutral Buildings', p. 2, p. 8
Available at: <https://carbonneutralcities.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/03/CNCA-Technical-Handbook-for-Carbon-Neutral-Buildings.pdf>
- [5] Carbon Neutral Cities Alliance, One Click LCA, architecture 2030, 2020, 'City Policy Framework for Dramatically Reducing Embodied Carbon'
Available at: <http://carbonneutralcities.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/City-Policy-Framework-for-Dramatically-Reducing-Embodied-Carbon.pdf>
- [6] Dimitriu S., Rusen M., 2022, Case Study Report, 'Making wood cities happen: New urban policies for a sustainable and carbon-neutral future', ISO391
- [7] Dimitriu S., Rusen M., Zagaglioni G., 2020, 'Socio-economic, planning and regulatory context in Early Adopter cities'. Technical Deliverable D7.3, Build-in-Wood project, GA no. 862820
- [8] appg, The All-Party Parliamentary Group Timber Industries, 2023, 'Timber Construction. Barriers and Solutions', A report for the All-Party Parliamentary Group for the Timber Industries
Available at: <https://cti-timber.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/07/CTI-APPG-Report-Barriers-and-solutions-to-timber-construction-online-1.pdf>
- [9] Lindblad F., 2020, Växjö Municipality's Planning Strategy to Increase the Construction of wooden Multi-Family Buildings, Institution of Logistics, School of Business and Economics
- [10] Strategic Programme for the Forest Sector, 2010, Finnish National Public Procurement Policy for Wood-Based Products
Available at: <https://www.yumpu.com/en/document/read/8375417/finnish-national-public-procurement-policy-for-wood-based>